

TABLE-1

		Viscosity of water (η_0) at			Density of water (ρ_0) at			
		30°=0.7975 cp 35°=0.7194 cp 40°=0.6529 cp			30°=0.9956 g cm ⁻³ 35°=0.9940 g cm ⁻³ 40°=0.9922 g cm ⁻³			
Solution	Molar concentration/M (C)	Coefficient of viscosity of solution/cp, η at			B coefficient (slope of linear plot of $\frac{\eta - \eta_0}{\eta_0 \sqrt{C}}$ vs $\sqrt{C}$) at			$\frac{dB}{dT}$ at
		30°	35°	40°	30°	35°	40°	35°
Phenol	0.025	—	0.7235	0.6565	0.230	0.213	0.192	-0.0037
	0.05	0.8104	0.7280	0.6592				
	0.08	0.8177	0.7311	0.6627				
	0.10	0.8228	0.7348	0.6664				
	0.15	—	0.7432	0.6758				
	0.20	0.8434	—	—				
Resorcinol	0.03	0.7994	—	—	0.189	0.216	0.244	+0.0054
	0.05	0.8060	0.7288	0.6620				
	0.10	0.8140	0.7374	0.6706				
	0.15	—	0.7458	0.6786				
	0.20	—	0.7538	0.6867				
	0.25	—	0.7625	0.6954				
p-cresol	0.05	0.7956	0.7315	0.6632	0.366	0.326	0.295	-0.0065
	0.075	0.8031	0.7380	0.6683				
	0.10	0.8101	0.7432	0.6740				
	0.12	0.8163	0.7484	0.6797				
Benzyl alcohol	0.025	—	0.7244	0.6576	0.222	0.272	0.260	—
	0.05	—	0.7296	0.6626				
	0.075	0.8140	0.7345	0.6670				
	0.10	0.8200	0.7397	0.6712				
	0.15	0.8309	0.7512	0.6816				
	0.20	0.8406	—	—				
0.30	0.8629	—	—					

temperature-dependence (an increase in B with temperature followed by a small drop beyond 35°; the $\frac{dB}{dT}$ at 35° for benzyl alcohol is, therefore, not quoted in Table 1), even though the values are close to those for p-cresol. This perhaps results from a partial overlapping of the structure-making and structure-breaking spheres of influence of the hydrophobic methylene and hydrophilic hydroxy groups, situated in close proximity in the side-chain, -CH₂OH, in benzyl alcohol. This gets a qualitative support from similar observations reported for the enthalpy of transfer of methanol from water to heavy water (as compared to that for higher alcohols)⁴, as well as the reported heats of transport of α -alanine and β -alanine in aqueous medium⁵.

References

1. T. S. SARMA and J. C. AHLUWALIA, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1973, 2, 203.
2. W. KAUFMANN, *Adv. Protein Chem.*, 1959, 14, 1.
3. S. K. SANJAL and S. K. MANDAL, in course of publication.
4. D. B. DAHLBERG, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1972, 76, 2045.
5. H. J. V. TYRRELL and M. ZAMAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 6216.

The Reaction of Isatin with Active Methylene Group. Part—I: Formation of 5-(2-Oxo-3-Indolinyldiene)-3-Aryl-2,4-Thiazolidindiones—
A New Class of Thioindigoid Dyes

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THE methylene group of substances having the structure -COCH₂NH- condenses readily with the carbonyl group of aldehydes and ketones¹. Active methylene group present in the 4-thiazolidinone ring has also been found to react with aryldiazonium salts² and isatino carbonyl group³.

A number of derivatives of isatin- β -thiosemicarbazone are reported to have antiviral activity⁴. Because of their usefulness and in order to examine the reactivity of the methylene group of 2,4-thiazolidindiones, we have undertaken the preparation of 5-(2-oxo-3-indolinyldiene)-3-aryl-2,4-thiazolidindiones which form a new class of thioindigoid dyes.

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NOTES

The synthesis of these thioindigoid dyes (3) and elucidation of their structures are reported in the present communication. 3-Aryl-2,4-thiazolidindiones (2), the starting materials, were prepared by the cyclization of symmetrical bis-arylthiocarbamides with 2-chloroacetic acid in glacial acetic acid medium. The nmr, ir and analytical data are consistent with the structures of these thiazolidindiones. They were further condensed with an equimolar quantity of isatin (1) in presence of fused sodium acetate in glacial acetic acid and acetic anhydride mixture forming the title compounds (3).

The assignment of structure of the dyes (3) was done on the basis of elemental analyses and ir spectral data.

The thioindigoid dyes formed different shades of orange to brick red crystals and dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid producing deep orange coloured solutions.

Experimental

All melting points were taken in open capillary tubes on a Gallenkamp apparatus and are uncorrected. The element analyses (C, H and N) were carried out on a Coleman Analyser. The infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 720 grating spectrophotometer as nujol mulls, while

the nmr spectra were run on a Varian A60-D spectrometer at probe temperature of 44.5° as CCl₄ or deuteriochloroform solutions using TMS as an internal standard.

Symmetrical bis-(3-chloro-2-methyl)phenyl thiocarbamide: This as well as other related symmetrical bis-arylthiocarbamides were prepared by the reaction of corresponding disubstituted anilines and carbon disulphide in presence of pyridine and iodine by the method of Fry⁸ with slight modification that the reaction mixture was heated under reflux and this gave high yields.

3-(3'-Chloro-2'-methyl)phenyl-2,4-thiazolidindione: A mixture of symmetrical bis-(3-chloro-2-methyl)phenyl thiocarbamide (3.2 g), monochloroacetic acid (1.0 g) and glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool, poured into cold water and filtered. The solid mass was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to give 3-(3'-chloro-2'-methyl)phenyl-2,4-thiazolidindione, yield 70%, m.p. 115°. Anal. Found: C, 49.56; H, 3.37; N, 5.62; S, 13.16. Calcd. for C₁₀H₈ClNO₂S; C, 49.69; H, 3.31; N, 5.80; S, 13.25%. IR (nujol): 1760(m), 1700(s), 1590(m), 1518(m) cm⁻¹. NMR (CDCl₃): δ 6.98-7.66 (m, 3H, ArH), 4.15 (s, 2H, CH₂), 2.20 (s, 3H, CH₃).

Similarly other 3-aryl-2,4-thiazolidindiones were prepared from reaction of different symmetrical bis-arylthiocarbamides and monochloroacetic acid in glacial acetic acid. Their yield, melting point, analytical and spectral data are reported in Table 1.

5-(2-Oxo-3-indolinylidene)-3-(5-chloro-2-methyl)phenyl-2,4-thiazolidindione: A mixture of 3-(5-chloro-2-methyl)phenyl-2,4-thiazolidindione (0.72 g; 3 mmole), isatin (0.51 g; 3.5 mmole), anhydrous sodium acetate (1.0 g), acetic anhydride (1.0 ml) and glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was placed in a

TABLE 1—3-ARYL-2,4-THIAZOLIDINDIONES^a(2)

Sl. No.	Substituents		m.p. °C	Molecular Formula	%C Found (Calcd.)	%H Found (Calcd.)	%N Found (Calcd.)	NMR Spectral data ^b		Characteristic IR bands:(cm ⁻¹)
	X	Y						δ _{SCH₂CO}	δ _X	
1.	2-CH ₃	5-Cl	118	C ₁₀ H ₈ ClNO ₂ S	49.72 (49.69)	3.21 (3.31)	5.65 (5.80)	3.96 (s, 2H)	2.23 (s, 3H)	1750(m), 1680(s), 1575(m), 1515(m)
2.	2-CH ₃	3-Cl	115	C ₁₀ H ₈ ClNO ₂ S	49.56 (49.69)	3.37 (3.31)	5.62 (5.80)	4.15 (s, 2H)	2.20 (s, 3H)	1760(m), 1700(s), 1590(m), 1518(m)
3.	4-CH ₃	3-Cl	180	C ₁₀ H ₈ ClNO ₂ S	49.81 (49.69)	3.26 (3.31)	5.68 (5.80)	3.93 (s, 2H)	2.36 (s, 3H)	1760(m), 1680(s), 1580(m), 1510(m)
4.	2-Cl	3-Cl	125	C ₉ H ₆ Cl ₂ NO ₂ S	41.18 (41.22)	2.05 (1.91)	5.26 (5.34)	4.20 (s, 2H)	—	1750(m), 1685(s), 1570(m), 1520(m)
5.	2-Cl	4-Cl	110	C ₉ H ₆ Cl ₂ NO ₂ S	41.25 (41.22)	1.87 (1.91)	5.22 (5.34)	4.19 (s, 2H)	—	1750(m), 1680(s), 1580(m), 1520(m)
6.	2-Cl	5-Cl	127	C ₉ H ₆ Cl ₂ NO ₂ S	41.29 (41.22)	1.76 (1.91)	5.29 (5.34)	4.19 (s, 2H)	—	1760(m), 1685(s), 1595(m), 1515(m)
7.	2-OCH ₃	5-Cl	155	C ₁₀ H ₈ ClNO ₂ S	46.57 (46.60)	2.98 (3.11)	5.41 (5.44)	4.18 (s, 2H)	3.83 (s, 3H)	1760(m), 1680(s), 1590(m), 1520(m)
8.	4-OCH ₃	3-Cl	167	C ₁₀ H ₈ ClNO ₂ S	46.48 (46.60)	3.05 (3.11)	5.31 (5.44)	4.15 (s, 2H)	4.00 (s, 3H)	1760(m), 1680(s), 1590(m), 1515(m)

^a Yields were in the range of 50-70%.

^b Aromatic protons appear at δ6.85-7.75 ppm as a multiplet of 3H intensity.

TABLE 2—5-(2-OXO-3-INDOLINYLIDENE)-3-(DISUBSTITUTED)PHENYL-2,4-THIAZOLIDINDIONES^a(3)

Sl. No.	Substituents		m.p. °C	Colour and shape of crystals	Molecular Formula	%C Found (Calcd.)	%H Found (Calcd.)	%N Found (Calcd.)	Characteristic IR bands (cm ⁻¹)
	X	Y							
	2-CH ₃	5-Cl	277-79	Orange, small needles	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₃ S	58.43 (58.32)	3.41 (3.00)	7.72 (7.55)	3200(w), 1745(m), 1685(s), 1615(m)
2.	2-CH ₃	3-Cl	284-86	Bright orange, crystals	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₃ S	58.15 (58.32)	3.30 (3.00)	7.65 (7.55)	3275(w), 1750(m), 1690(s), 1645(s), 1620(s)
3.	4-CH ₃	3-Cl	>310 dec.	Orange, fine crystals	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₃ S	58.60 (58.32)	2.92 (3.00)	7.85 (7.55)	3215(w), 1740(m), 1675(s), 1655(s), 1615(m)
4.	2-Cl	3-Cl	323-25	Brick red, microcrystals	C ₁₇ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	52.01 (52.19)	2.29 (2.06)	6.93 (7.16)	3400(m), 1745(m), 1690(s), 1620(m)
5.	2-Cl	4-Cl	161-62 ^b	Orange yellow, powder	C ₁₇ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	51.86 (52.19)	1.93 (2.06)	7.18 (7.16)	3300(w), 1740(m), 1700(m), 1645(s), 1620(m)
6.	2-Cl	5-Cl	266-68	Orange red, fine crystals	C ₁₇ H ₉ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	51.90 (52.19)	2.23 (2.06)	7.40 (7.16)	3450(br,w), 1740(m), 1690(m), 1640(s), 1615(s)
7.	2-OCH ₃	5-Cl	275-76	Bright orange, long needles	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₄ S	55.85 (55.90)	2.91 (2.86)	6.96 (7.24)	3400(br,w), 1745(m), 1685(s), 1615(w)
8.	4-OCH ₃	3-Cl	330-33	Deep orange, fine crystals	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ O ₄ S	56.18 (55.90)	3.05 (2.86)	7.02 (7.24)	3200(w), 1740(m), 1675(s), 1615(m)

^a Yields were in the range of 80-95%.

^b Shrinks at 130°.

round bottom flask. The flask was immersed in an oil bath preheated to 150-160°. The reaction mixture became orange at this temperature and within 10 min orange crystals began to appear. Heating under reflux was continued for 3 hr. It was then cooled and treated with excess of hot water. The thioindigoid dye was filtered and washed successively with hot water, dilute acetic acid and finally with ethanol. Recrystallization from ethanol afforded orange needles, yield 90%, m.p. 277-79°. Anal. Found: C, 58.43; H, 3.41; N, 7.72. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₁ClN₂O₃S; C, 58.32; H, 2.99; N, 7.55%. IR (nujol): 3200 (w, N-H stretch), 1745 (m, C=O stretch), 1685 (s, C=O stretch), 1615 (m) cm⁻¹.

The general procedure exemplified above was employed for synthesis of all the thioindigoid dyes. Their properties and characteristic ir spectral bands are reported in Table 2.

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References

1. A. J. HILL and H. R. HENZL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **46**, 2806.
2. P. N. BHARGAVA and M. R. CHAURASIA, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1969, **58**, 896.
3. R. P. RAO, *Chem. Ber.*, 1959, **92**, 2600.
4. D. J. BAUER and P. W. SADLER *Brit. J. Pharmacol.*, 1960, **15**, 101.
5. H. S. FRY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, **35**, 1539.

Reaction of Ninhydrin with Aromatic Amines and Ureas

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THE reactions of ninhydrin (I) with aromatic amines were studied by a number of workers¹⁻⁴. Several reports are available on the reactions of ninhydrin with ureas⁵⁻⁷. The objective of our present investigation was to have some qualitative idea about the reactivity of ninhydrin towards nucleophilic addition using poor organic nitrogen nucleophiles and to prepare various conjugated systems from these reactions. In continuation of our previous studies⁸⁻¹⁰ on the reactions of ninhydrin, we report here the syntheses of compounds (II)-(VII). These compounds appear to be new and are not reported in the literature.

Structures were assigned to these compounds on the basis of their nitrogen content, ir spectral data (Table 1) and formation of derivatives. 2,4-DNP did not react with the second carbonyl group of the mentioned compounds probably due to steric hindrance^{8,10}. Compounds (II) and (IV) gave positive Lucas test indicating the presence of tertiary-OH groups. It is not clear why the adduct (II) in the case of α -naphthylamine did not undergo dehydration while the condensation product (III) was obtained in the case of β -naphthylamine. One probable explanation may be that the steric interaction due to the naphthalene ring becomes sufficiently strong to prevent the formation of the planar structure for the condensation